

MAIN METHODS AND MODELS OF FORMATION OF LEGAL TERMS IN GERMAN LANGUAGE

Mirzayev F.D.

Chief of cabinet of the Department of State-Legal Disciplines and Ensuring of Human Rights Protection of the Academy of MIA, major
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Abstract. *Despite the fact that there are many studies devoted to the study of terminology in various fields in order to systematize terminological units, analyze their lexical properties, determine their operational characteristics in the practice of linguistics, some aspects of the terminological system have not yet been sufficiently studied. For example, the most effective ways and methods of forming legal terminology in German language are not defined as linguistic rules. Based on these phenomena, today it is relevant to consider the features of word formation of legal terms in German language. The relevance of studying the word formation of terminological units in the field of legal studies of German language is also associated with knowledge of the methods and means of word formation, which contributes to mastering the vocabulary of the studied language, which has not only theoretical but also direct practical significance for mastering a foreign language. This article examines issues related to the distinction between word-formation terms, such as a word-formation model, a word-formation type, a method and means of word-formation. Based on practical experience, legal terms extracted through a continuous sample from legal texts, as well as from German-Russian legal dictionaries, were used as research material. The study revealed that the most effective ways of forming terminological units of German language in the field of jurisprudence are compounding and affixation and a combination of these two methods. Most terms are independent groups of words consisting of nouns, and the main word-formation is the prefix-suffix and suffix models.*

Keywords: legal term, word-formation method, word-formation model, compounding, affixation, prefix-suffix model, suffix model.

Issues related to the study of terminology have not lost their importance for a long time. Researchers focus on the semantic and structural aspects of problems related to the system of terms and concepts of the terminological field. Legal terminology is currently of special interest to theoretical linguists and practical researchers as a tool of legal communication. When considering the meaning, structure, and impact of legal terms, it is important to study the word formation features of terminological units, because “the semantics of the terminological unit has its place in the national lexicon and is formally expressed by the structural features of the term” [4, p. 44-45].

The purpose of this study is to determine the most effective methods and models for the formation of legal terminological units. The research material is the terminological units that form the basis of the lexical minimum necessary for learning, and were selected from legal texts and legal dictionaries. The issue of formation of terminological units is actively discussed by experts in the field of general and applied terminology. The problem of the formation of terms and terminological combinations for many years (A.A. Reformatsky [5], E.K. Drezen [6], S.V. Grinev-Grinevich [7], V.P. Danilenko [8], V. M. Leychik [9]), as well as other foreign linguists (H. Felber [10], Kyo Kageura [11], S. Pavel, D. Nole [12]) attracted attention. The emergence of terminological units is a rather complex process that is directly related to the laws of development

of a particular language. As E.K.Drezen noted: “the possibility of creating new terms, the possibility of establishing connections between the form and meaning of the term is determined by the structural features of the language” [6 , p. 128-129].

Before conducting a word-formation analysis of our selected material, it is necessary to distinguish and briefly describe the main concepts such as word formation model, word formation tools, word formation method, word formation type. The main unit of the word-formation system is the type of word-formation, which is understood as a set of similar units united by the specificity of the stimulus word, adverb and word-formative part of speech. Within one type of word formation, different ways of combining the forming stem and the word forming affix can be given. Currently, researchers (I.I. Kovalik, B.N. Golovin) consider the word formation system to be a collection of word formation types [13, 14]. A word-formation method is a combination of several word-formation types characterized by the same type of form-maker, regardless of its material representation and word-formation meaning.

If we turn to history, attention has been paid to word formation since the time of Makhmud Koshgari, in which mainly two methods of word formation were active. In general, almost all of the studies conducted on word formation in world linguistics are based on word formation, what are their methods, and their appearance. In Uzbek linguistics, the study of word formation methods by the well-known linguist scientist A.Gulomov dedicated to revealing the essence of this issue, and in the research works of academician A. Khojiev, there are views on word formation methods.

In German M.D. Stepanova distinguishes the following methods of word formation:

- word addition (Zusammensetzung/Komposition);
- word production (Ableitung/ Derivation);
- formation of compound words (Zusammenbildung);
- creation of abbreviations (Kurzwortbildung/Abkürzung);
- transition to another part of speech (Konversion/Wortartwechsel) [15].

Each method of word formation has certain patterns. Word formation model is a structure with a generalized lexical-categorical content and organized based on general laws [15, 179 p.]. The term “word formation model” can also be used as a synonym for word formation type. Such an understanding of the model of word formation is expressed in the works of E.A. Zemskoy, A.N. Tikhonov. [16, 17]. A word-former is the “material” used to create new lexical units. In the German language, various affixes, the root of the word, as well as the historical alternation of sounds (ablaut, umlaut) can serve as word-forming tools.

When analyzing German legal terminology, it is clear that the vocabulary of this terminological system is mainly represented by nouns, and nouns serve as the basis for the absolute majority of terms in word combinations. Such a morphological feature of legal terms determines the wide distribution of certain methods and models of word formation. In the process of systematic analysis of the words of the selected sample, it was found that the most effective methods of formation of German terminology in the field of jurisprudence are affixation and combination.

Affixation is the addition of word-forming affixes to the forming base to form a new word. Affix (formant) - a morpheme that is added to the base to form a new word. Taking into account the meaning of the creator, G.O. Vinokur notes that the affix can form a meaning only when it is combined with the base, which allows to see this base from another point of view [18, p. 421].

Based on this method, the following patterns of formation of German legal terms can be seen:

- prefix model;
- suffix model;
- prefix-suffix model.

The prefix model is the formation of new words by adding a prefix to the base that forms it.

The following terms may serve as examples:

- an- → der Anspruch – claim, demand;
- be- → der Betrüger – fraudster, die Begründung – evidence, proof;
- ein- → der Einfall – breaking into;
- er- → die Ermordung – murder;
- ge- → das Gemenge – fight, das Gericht – court;
- ver- → die Vernachlässigung – disregard, indifference.

Analysis of word formation has shown that this pattern is not widespread enough in the formation of legal terms in German. Prefixes are mainly used to form verbs:

- be- → beschweren – to aggravate, beschuldigen – to blame;
- ver- → verhören – to interrogate, verpfänden – to pledge;
- ent- → entschädigen – to pay the damage, entschärfen – to neutralize.

A fruitful method for forming terminological units is based on the addition of various suffixes to the stem. It is worth mentioning that the suffix can be added to the root, changing its meaning and indicating that the resulting word belongs to a certain lexical and grammatical word group. In the formation of legal terms, adverbs meaning participant, action, state, tool, place of action are used more often. As an example, we will focus on the terms formed with the most common suffixes:

- ung (denotes an action or the result of an action) →
die Klagsicherung – securing a claim;
die Ermordung – premeditated murder;
- land (used to designate people by profession) →
der Antragsteller – claimant;
der Richter – judge;
das Opfer – the victim;
- schaft (gives the importance of generalization) →
die Patenschaft – guardianship;
die Bürgerschaft – citizenship.

The most effective form of word formation in German legal terminology is the prefix-suffix form, in which both the prefix and the suffix act as word-forming affixes. Among the legal terms based on this model of word formation, the most common are nouns with the prefix an-, be-, er-, ver- and the suffixes -ung, -er. Usually, they are formed using suffixes corresponding to verbs, which in turn are formed from prefixes.

An__er:

- der Angreifer (← angreifen) – the attacking person;
- der Anstifter (← anstiften) – instigator, conspirator;

Be_____ung:

die Belästigung (← belästigen) – disturbing (*the peace*) ;
die Benachteiligung (← benachteiligen) – causing damage;
Ver_____ung:
die Verschwörung (← verschwören) – conspiracy (*hidden*) ;
die Vernehmung (← vernehmen) – interrogation.

In these word formations, the prefix structure has the main semantic meaning, and the postfixal element indicates a generalized meaning (represents the process, result, or executor of an action) and determines in advance whether the word belongs to a certain lexical-grammatical category. Another effective way to form German legal terms is word combinations. A word combination means a syntactic structure — a speech unit — formed as a result of combining two or more independent words on the basis of a subordinate grammatical relationship (adaptation, management, or agreement), which indicates the name of things and events in existence. M.D. According to Stepanova: “combination is one of the oldest methods and at the same time the most effective way of forming words on nouns in German language” [19, p. 109].

As one of the main methods for making terminological units, the productivity of word combinations was used by V.M. Pavlov: “In the practice of speaking in German language, word combinations are freely and well used for expressing and generalizing concepts formed in the mind of an individual in one situation or for the contextual-general construction of complex words with a certain relative stability in a short time and for a narrow group of people” [20, 20 b.].

It should be noted that most of the legal terms are compound nouns, while adjectives and compound verbs are less common.

According to the components that make up complex terms, the following word formation models can be distinguished:

– noun + noun: der Bereitschaftswagen (Bereitschaft + connecting part -s + Wagen) - police car on duty; das Beschwerderecht (Beschwerde + Recht) - right of appeal, das Tatwerkzeug - weapon of crime, die Vollzugsanstalt (Vollzug + conjunction -s + anstalt) – place of deprivation of liberty.

– adjective + noun: die Falschverdächtigung (falsch + Verdächtigung)– wrong, false suspicion; new definition of die Neuformulierung (neu + Formulierung)-(law); die Naturalherstellung (natural + Herstellung) – compensation for damage naturally.

– verb+noun (as a rule, in this model, the verb is presented as the preceding root morpheme): die Einfahrtsbewilligung (Einfahr (einfahren) + Bewilligung) – permission to enter (*the territory of a country*) , der Durchsuchungsbefehl (Durchsuchung (durchsuchen) + Befehl) - search warrant, der Wohnsitz (Wohn (wohnen) + Sitz) - place of residence, das Mahnschreiben (Mahn (mahnen) + Schreiben) - written warning.

The analysis of the models discussed above showed that the most common word combination models in the formation of legal terms are “noun + noun” and “verb + noun” models.

Syntax in German is a multifaceted and extremely complex phenomenon. In addition, the legal lexicon of German language is characterized by multi-content terms, the formation model of which can include several models of word structure at the same time. An example of this is die Strafprozeßordnung (Criminal Procedure Code), which is formed by combining the two models “noun + noun” (Prozeß + Ordnung) and “verb + noun” (Straf (strafen) + Prozeßordnung).

An analysis of the above examples shows that the components involved in the composition of legal terms are not only root morphemes for example, die Pfandreife (expiration of the pledge

period, giving the mortgagee the right to apply for the sale of the pledged thing (at a public auction) to pay off the debt, das Schuldrecht (compulsory right), das Tatziel (purpose of crime), but also words formed by affixation (e.g. das Gerichtsorgan (judicial body), die Zeugnispflicht (giving testimony obligation), die Fahrlässigkeitsdelikt (a crime committed due to carelessness), that is, there is also a case where word combinations are proportional by affixation.

The most effective models of formation of legal terms based on combination of word combination and affixation are models in which the first component is formed by the root morpheme, and the second component is formed by affixation. Examples are terminological units such as der Schuldspruch (conviction), der Sachbefund (result of examination of something), die Strafverbüßung (sentencing), die Eheaufhebung (marriage annulment) , which involve two forms of word formation: collocation and affixation. The first part of these legal terms is formed by root morpheme (Sach-, Schuld-, Straf-, Ehe-), the second part is made by affixation according to the prefix-addition model. It should be noted that in some cases the connecting element (e)s can be used between the components, for example der Rechtsanspruch (legal claim), die Volksversammlung (people's council), die Landesvertretung (representation of the country). Prefix die Strafanstalt (place of deprivation of liberty), die Tatverantwortung (responsibility for crime), das Eheverhältnisse (marriage relationship) or affix die Lohnforderung (claim for wages), die Ehenötigung (forcing marriage), der Straftäter (criminal) models based on the combination of the stem morpheme with the part formed by models formed by affixation of both contents are less productive (die Sicherheitsmaßnahme (security measure), die Ordnungsverstöße (violation of administrative rules), die Zeugnishaftigkeit (ability to testify), die Prüfungsordnung (verification order).

In conclusion, it should be noted that legal terminology is a separate layer of lexicology and is characterized by a number of lexical and structural features, including certain models and methods of forming terminological units. The main methods are word combination and affixation, which are complex and multifaceted phenomena, and in some cases they can be combined with each other. The productivity of the main models in the formation of terminological units in jurisprudence is determined by the morphological characteristics of these units. Most legal terms are nouns. Within the affixation method, prefix-suffix and suffix models are most often used to form nouns, as part of a word combination, nouns are usually formed using the “noun + noun” and “verb + noun” models. In connection with these morphological features, the above models are the most effective in the formation of terminological units of the legal field.

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